

Climateurope2

Project management guidelines

Deliverable 8.1

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Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the management and administrative procedures of the Climateurope2 Project in order to facilitate efficient project execution as well as high-quality project results. The document will provide the Climateurope2 consortium with a concise reference to the project management structure, tasks and responsibilities at all levels of project execution. It establishes the management bodies and responsibilities in order to ensure timely and correct production of the results and deliverables as well as the quality and risk management plan.

1 Introduction

This document specifically covers the following areas:

- Administrative project management processes that ensure accurate financial reporting and justification of the work being carried out.
- General project management processes that ensure tight coordination of project activities resulting in high-quality deliverables.
- An internal communication strategy that ensures clear and effective communication between the Partners and that allows for the early escalation and the timely resolution of possible issues concerning management and the technical work.

Changes of this document

The guidance is a living document. It will be regularly updated throughout the entire duration of the project to reflect the changes in - and evolution of - the project.

The Project Manager is responsible for updating and making it available in the internal project wiki.

2 Project management

2.1 Management structure

The main governing bodies of Climateurope2 are shown on the picture below.

Figure 1. Climateurope2 management structure

2.2 Management bodies

The Climateurope2 project organisation, roles and responsibilities are described in the Governance structure of the Consortium Agreement (clause 6 Governance structure). This table summarises their main tasks.

Table 1 Management bodies

Management Body	Composition	Tasks
General Assembly (GA)	All partners (beneficiaries and associated partners). A representative of each partner.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The GA is the decision-making body of the consortium. ● Each Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide. ● Initiatives and actions on which GA takes decisions are listed in the Consortium Agreement. ● Voting and veto rights are described in the Consortium Agreement.
Management Board (MB)	Project Coordinator Project Manager Technical Manager Work Package leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review of the project progress on a regular basis; ● Making decisions on day-to-day issues. ● Resource allocation, review/approval of Periodic Reports and Deliverables, preparation of project reviews, and coordination of exploitation plans. ● Organisation of monthly conference calls and support of the members' involvement in decision-making. ● In the case when the Management Board cannot obtain consensus to make a decision, bringing the issue to the General Assembly and bringing to a vote if required.
Coordination team (BSC)	Project Coordinator (PC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Keeping the entire project running smoothly. ● Gathering and dispensing the needed information and updating and coordinating the work throughout the project life cycle. ● Ensuring the internal communication in the consortium, meeting project milestones and quality control of deliverables. ● Acting as the official point of contact between the Commission and the Beneficiaries
	The Technical Manager (TM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensuring that the scientific and technical objectives of the project are met. ● Helping the PC to lead the definition of the high-level technical strategy and coordinates the team project to implement it. ● Technical presentations of project progress to external parties and ensuring the appropriate involvement and visibility of the members of the project. ● Close collaboration with the PC and the PM to provide clear and accurate Periodic Reports.

Management Body	Composition	Tasks
	Project Manager (PM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The day-to-day execution of the project. ● Ensuring the timely achievement of project objectives and deliverables by continuously monitoring the project progress against the plan of record. ● Identify and track issues as well as propose suitable corrective actions (i.e. resource reallocation, task force creation, etc.) that might require a formal decision by the General Assembly. ● Calling the General Assembly meetings, as well as reviewing, compiling and distributing Minutes and Actions. ● Defining the procedures for change management (proposed changes to the plan of record), risk management, quality assurance and IPR management. ● Administrative and financial management of the project. ● Monitoring internal use of resources on a 6-month basis. ● Provisioning of Periodic Reports and Financial Statements, and ensuring efficient distribution of EU funding. ● Acting as the official point of contact between the Commission and the Beneficiaries.
WP leaders (WPL)	WP1: TECNALIA/BSC WP2: BSC/CERFACS WP3: CMCC WP4: UBREMEN/ECO WP5: CLIMATE-KIC/HEREON WP6: CPN/WR WP7: BSC/CMCC WP8: BSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordinating the scientific and technical work of their respective Work Packages. ● Planning and control of all activities within the Work Package. ● Preparing deliverables and collecting the contributions from other partners participating in the respective Work Packages for internal and external reports. ● Participating in periodical meetings and arranging additional technical meetings when necessary. ● Supporting the Technical Manager in coordinating cross-work package relationships within the appropriate activity area. ● Actively participate in the regular project-related meetings as well as prepare technical and status presentations as required. ● Analysing the documentation of the outputs generated along the project to collect relevant information on potential marketable products. ● Supporting the partners in dealing with IPR issues as well as in negotiating joint exploitation agreements.

Management Body	Composition	Tasks
External Advisory Board (EAB)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the external evaluation of the project progress. • Providing recommendations for new actions and activities in the area by liaising with the MB and participating in the general assemblies. • Increasing the project visibility and strengthening its links to international programmes and other activities outside Europe.

3 Internal communication

3.1 Meetings

A part of the communication process, meetings are a key tool to monitor the project lifecycle. Regular meetings (online or face-to-face) will be held to ensure that all procedures are understood and properly implemented.

Table 2 Project meetings

Project Body	Key responsibilities	Meetings frequency	Participants
Coordination team	Overall progress and quality of the project	Weekly	BSC
Management Board (MB)	Follow-up of status and progress of WPs, WP tasks and synergies/alignment of work.	On monthly basis. Organised by the coordinator.	Coordination team + WP leaders.
WP Leaders (WPL)	Oversee overall progress and quality of WP and WP tasks Monthly	At least, on monthly basis but it is up to WP leaders to determine the frequency with partners	WP leaders + task leaders and WP partners.
General Assembly (GA)	To take decisions on operational and management issues and it is responsible for all decisions of general nature within the frame of the Grant Agreement.	On annual basis. Organised by the coordinator and the partner host.	All partners.
External Advisory Board (EAB)	To make recommendations on project objective achievements and impact.	At least four times during the project duration. Back-to-back with General Assemblies.	EAB members and coordination team (if needed)

The initiator of the meeting (coordinator, WP leaders, etc) is responsible for:

- sending the meeting request,
- organising the meeting locations and facilities (if needed),
- ensuring that meeting minutes are sent to the Coordinator and archived in the project wiki.

3.2 Internal mailing lists

Having proper communication within the project is one of the main goals of good project management. The Climateurope2 project has developed several internal tools to improve the information flows within the project.

The website and the internal wiki will be the main tools for the project communication with the outer world and internally, respectively. The partners are strongly encouraged to visit them and send feedback to the project office. A set of mailing lists, which have been pre-populated by the Coordinator, are available for all the partners. Some examples of the addresses created are:

- General lists:
 - climateurope2@bsc.es: this list to all contacts in each partner institution.
 - research_ce2@bsc.es: this list is addressed to all researchers in the project.
 - advisoryboard_ce2@bsc.es: this list is addressed to the External Advisory Board (EAB) members.
 - management_ce2@bsc.es: this list addresses those contacts in charge of legal, financial and administrative issues in each partner institution.
- WP lists:
 - wpleaders_ce2@bsc.es: this list is addressed only to the WP leaders.
 - wp1_ce2@bsc.es
 - wp2_ce2@bsc.es
 - wp3_ce2@bsc.es
 - wp4_ce2@bsc.es
 - wp5_ce2@bsc.es
 - wp6_ce2@bsc.es
 - wp7_ce2@bsc.es:
 - wp8_ce2@bsc.es

The control of WP lists will be handed back to the WP leaders. The instructions on how to manage the mailing lists can be found in the wiki. The coordinator will moderate general lists and WP list will be unmoderated. Partners' remote internal communications can be held through online platforms. The preparation of minutes is strongly recommended, and any minutes should be uploaded to the wiki.

3.3 Project website and internal wiki

Climateurope2 website

The project website public link is available here:

<https://climateurope2.eu/>

WP7 is responsible for the management and update of the project website. Details will be provided in the deliverable *D7.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan*.

Climateurope2 internal wiki

The Climateurope2 internal wiki is a private section of the web area, and can be accessed via the external website or directly through the link <http://earth.bsc.es/climateurope2/>. It is only available after registration, which is controlled by the coordination team.

This wiki is an important communication tool of the consortium. It has been designed to exchange documents and as a repository of discussions and information in general. The access to the wiki is subject to coordinator's approval. All partners have been invited to register and encouraged to use this tool.

The information is constantly supervised by the coordination team and updated by partners and coordinator.

3.4 Project documents

3.4.1 Types and templates

The Climateurope2 project has different templates depending on the type of reporting and WP, as listed below:

- Six-monthly report template: WP8
- Deliverable template
- Milestone template
- Agenda Template
- Minutes Template
- Blank Climateurope2 pptx template
- Risk and Issue process templates

Templates are provided and stored in the project internal wiki under the "Templates and logos" section". All templates are aligned with the visual identity of Climateurope2, and those used for public communication have the EU acknowledgement emblem.

WP7 leader institution is responsible for maintaining and storing project templates.

Figure 2. Climateurope2 wiki: templates and logos

3.4.2 Documents naming rules

To ensure the track of document versions and avoid missing information, Climateurope2 has foreseen general naming rules for the documents released in the project:

Deliverables and milestones must respect the general naming rule

DX.X_vN
MY.Y_vN

- DX.X represents the deliverable number
- vN.n represents a simplified version number for the internally reviewed versions (as we can rely on the project wiki)
- v0.x (for v0.1 to v0.9 for initial drafts versions)
- v1.1 (v1.2, etc) ... for complete version, under review and candidates for official delivery
- v1 for the reviewed official version submitted to the Commission
- v2, v3, etc for further updates

4 Quality assurance

4.1 Deliverables and milestones format

Templates for the deliverables and milestones has been created in WP7 and are available in the project wiki as mentioned in section 3.

4.2 Deliverables and milestones review and submission

The list of deliverables and milestones y available in the project wiki and regularly updated by the Deliverable Leader. The Internal review process goes through stages (depicted in Figure 2) to ensure that any issues concerning the overall quality is resolved before final approval and submission of deliverables to the EC or publication of the report. The Coordinator is responsible for the Quality assurance process that starts 1'5 months before the official deadline.

Review Process proposed:

Figure 3. Deliverable/milestone review process

1 Draft preparation

- The Coordinator will send an alert message to the Deliverable leader and to the corresponding WP Leader.
- It is up to the Deliverable leader to organise the way to collect the information and organise partners' contribution to the document.
- A full draft of the deliverable/milestone should be made available to the Coordinator and WP leader in the next 20 days. Partners involved will contribute to the deliverable/milestone along this period.

2 Deliverable review

- The WP leader, supported by the Deliver leader, will appoint a reviewer. This reviewer should be an expert in the topic (internal or external) not directly involved in the preparation of the deliverable/milestone.
- The WP leader, Deliverable leader, partners involved and reviewer expert, will have 15 days to grant approval or suggest modifications to this draft. The approval of the final version is granted by the reviewer.
- In case a deeper re-work appears necessary, the reviewer(s) are asked to provide constructive suggestions for improvement in writing to the Deliverable Leader and WP leader. Upon receiving the suggestions for improvement, the Coordination Team works with the Deliverable Lead beneficiary to determine the schedule to complete the Deliverable.
- The Deliverable leader is responsible for the final check and implementation of the potential changes. They will have ten days for this process. The final version should be made available in the project wiki.

3 Deliverable submission

- The Coordinator will be responsible for collecting the final deliverable and submitting it to the Research Participant Portal tool.
- Final version will be available in the project wiki under the section "Deliverables and Milestones" (Figure X). Stable versions should always be provided as an additional PDF file. Deliverables and milestones documents must follow the naming rules mentioned above.

Figure 4. Climateurope2 wiki: deliverables and milestones section

Note: This process is also applied to milestones review and submission.

5 Monitoring and KPIs

5.1 Monitoring

The Coordination team observes and checks the progress of the project keeping a systematic internal review.

Technical monitoring:

- The scientific work will be supervised by the Coordinator and supported by the WP leaders. Each WP leader shall organise the work and the communication within their work package. If needed, the Coordinator may ask for a summary status report at any stage of the project.
- The WP leaders and the Coordinator will meet remotely on a monthly, during the first GA a different periodicity might be decided; extra meetings are foreseen upon request. These meetings will report the progress of the work done and deviations of the project plan, if any. The minutes will be made available in the project wiki.

Deliverables/Milestones monitoring

The preparation of deliverables is responsibility of Deliverable leaders under the supervision of WP leader. A set of templates has been and they will be available in the project wiki. The monitoring process is explained in section 4 of this deliverable.

5.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Definition

The Climateurope2 project will define a set of KPIs in order to monitor the proper development of the project.

- KPIs are aligned with WP objectives and have a specific target to be achieved by the end of the project.
- WP leaders will define KPIs according to the objectives and characteristics of each work package including its duration, thus some of the indicators may apply only at specific stages of the project.
- The list of KPIs will be available in the project wiki under the section "WP8 Project management".
- It is recommended to use quantitative KPIs to facilitate their measurement.

Measurement and refining

- KPIs measuring is planned on a six-monthly basis, and results are presented during the corresponding annual General Assemblies.
- In case the WP activity developed makes it inappropriate to continue reporting on the same KPIs or happened that they are not relevant over time, this KPI list will be refined to facilitate the reporting.
- The Management Board is responsible for ensuring the KPIs follow-up.

6 Reporting

The Climateurope2 project has established two reporting levels:

- Internal reporting: Partners reporting to the coordinator.
- External reporting: Periodic reporting to EC.

Figure 5. Climateurope2 reporting schedule

6.1 Internal reporting

The internal reporting will remain within the consortium; all parties are entitled to report to the coordinator. This reporting is mainly focused on the main deviations of the Project plan as well as the deliverables submission monitoring.

- Every six months the Project Manager will collect information about the progress of WP activities, a brief description of the technical work done, and dissemination/communication activities.
- All partners are entitled to complete this internal report according to the template available in the project wiki under the section "Templates and logos".
- Four to three weeks prior to the six months' deadline, the Project Manager will submit the template to be filled in by the partners. The completed information shall be forwarded to the Coordinator not later than six-month deadline.
- The six-monthly reporting is set up in a way that it supports periodic reporting.

6.2 External reporting

The Climateurope2 project reports to European Commission according to its rules and through the Research Participant Portal. This external reporting consists of two parts: a financial report and a technical report.

Once the Periodic Reporting session is open on the EC website, the Coordinator will send an alert email to the consortium for collecting the information and providing the corresponding instructions.

Individual Financial report:

Each partner is responsible for its financial report to the European Commission. The financial statements submission is made individually by each partner through the grant management system, which is available in the Research Participant Portal.

The rules and explanations for fulfilling the financial reports can be found on the Horizon Europe Online Manual under the section Periodic reports and also in the project wiki

The process is summarised in the following picture:

Figure 6. Financial reporting to EC process

Technical report:

This report consists of two parts, Part A and Part B, and the Coordinator is responsible for submitting both parts through the Research Participant Portal. All partners are responsible for providing the information to the Coordinator in order to complete the technical report which describes the project progress during the period reported.

The internal reporting (see above section 5.2.1) is the basis of this technical report. The process is summarised in the following picture:

Figure 7. Scientific reporting to EC process

7 Risk management

1.1 Risks management

The Climateurope2 project has established the following process to ensure the proper monitoring of projects risks:

Figure 8. Risk management process

The above process will be applied to each WP for monitoring project risks. The following table shows the management bodies involved in the process responsibilities and frequency of risks follow up.

The coordination team is responsible for ensuring the whole process.

Table 3. Risks management

Who	What	When	Documents to be used
Coordination team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is responsible for coordinating risks management. • To collect WPs risks and integrate them into the risks matrix. • To ensure the follow-up of risks status. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On a monthly basis. • Risk information is collected one week before each Management Board meeting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table of risks (available in the wiki) • Risks matrix integrated • Integrated mitigation plan (if needed)

Who	What	When	Documents to be used
WP Leaders (WPL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To identify the foreseen and unforeseen risks of their WP. ● To report to the Management Board using the WP risks register template (available in the wiki) ● To propose mitigation measures, if needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On a monthly basis but it is up to WP leaders to determine the frequency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Table of risks ● WP risks register ● WP risks mitigation plan (if needed)
Management Board (MB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To analyse and assess project risks based on the information provided by WP leaders. ● To agree on the mitigation measures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● On a monthly basis. ● If needed, extra meetings devoted to risks management are also foreseen. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Table of risks ● Integrated Risks matrix ● Integrated mitigation plan

1.2 Risks management documents

There are several documents that will help to collect the risks information:

- Grant Agreement Part A: It includes the table of risks foreseen in the project.
- WP risks register: this document is a table with several columns that include, among other information, the likelihood and impact score of the risk and mitigation action plan when needed. Unforeseen risks will be also included in this table.
- Risk matrix: this table summarizes the list of risks and gives an overview of the risks status.
- Templates of these documents are available in the project wiki.

Figure 9. Risks label classification

Risks matrix will reflect the level of risks according to the labels that are classified in Low, Medium and High. Decisions on the action plan will be taken accordingly as shown in the table below:

Table 4. Risks rating

Rating	Decision	Description
HIGH	Avoid	Find a way to avoid the risk. For example, by taking a different approach, not doing something, using different tools, etc.
MEDIUM	Mitigate	Find a way to reduce the likelihood of the risk occurring or the severity of the impact if the risk does occur.
LOW	Accept	The risk is acceptable. The project can move forward, and mitigation of the risk is a low priority.

8 Data protection

The Climateurope2 project will need to manage an amount of data not only from the partners but also from other key actors in the field of climate services that might contribute to the project outcomes such as public and private stakeholders, energy users, public institutions, etc.

A protocol for data protection will be defined to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This document will include aspects such as consent procedure, personal data profile of the participants or expiration of time of storage. The protocol will be regularly discussed with the project partners to remind them how to proceed and included as a specific section in the deliverable D8.3 Data Management Plan.

The coordination team will monitor and take the corresponding measures for mitigation of potential risks of privacy and confidentiality issues that may arise related to data security, with special attention paid to the data held in the project resource repository. This topic will be included in the periodic meetings mentioned in section 3.1 of this deliverable.